
Research Article

A new combination in *Xylosma* (Salicaceae)

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Abstract: A new combination *Xylosma zollingeriana* (Miq.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar is made here for *Rottlera zollingeriana* Miq. In addition, lectotype is designated here for *R. zollingeriana* Miq. to fix the identity and to avoid the misapplication of name.

Keywords: Endemic, Indonesia, *Rottlera zollingeriana*

Introduction

The genus *Xylosma* G.Forst. consists of about 112 species, distributed in tropical and subtropical Asia to Pacific, and tropical and subtropical America (POWO, 2025). In Indonesia, the genus is represented by 4 species, namely *X. luzonensis* (C.Presl) Clos, *X. papuana* Gilg, *X. suluensis* Merr. and *X. sumatrana* Slooten. Miquel (1859) published the name *Rottlera zollingeriana* based on the specimens collected by H. Zollinger from Java, Indonesia. Later, while working on Flora Malesiana, H.O. Sleumer (1906–1993) identified these specimens as a species of the genus *Xylosma* and made a new combination on these herbarium sheets, but did not publish the combination. After studying these specimens, we found that Sleumer was correct and these specimens belong to the genus *Xylosma*. Therefore, a new combination is made here for *Rottlera zollingeriana* Miq. under the genus *Xylosma* as *X. zollingeriana* (Miq.) Sleumer ex R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar. To fix the identity and to avoid the misapplication of name, lectotype is designated here for *Rottlera zollingeriana* Miq. as per the guidelines and recommendations of Article 9 of ICN (Turland et al., 2018).

Figure 1: Lectotype of *Rottlera zollingeriana* Miq. (G00364048, © Conservatoire et Jardin botaniques de la Ville de Genève)

Figure 2: Isolectotype of *Rottlera zollingeriana* Miq. (G00364047, © Conservatoire et Jardin botaniques de la Ville de Genève)

New combination

Xylosma zollingeriana (Miq.) Sleumer ex R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. Nov.*

≡ *Rottlera zollingeriana* Miq., Fl. Ned. Ind. 1(2): 394. 1859.

Lectotype (designated here): Indonesia, Java, 1847, *H. Zollinger 3174* (G00364048!, Figure 1);
isoelectotypes G00364047! (Figure 2), L0011395!, U0115710!.

Distribution: Endemic to Java, Indonesia.

Notes: The better-preserved specimen G00364047, is designated here as the lectotype for the name
Rottlera zollingeriana Miq. as it agrees well with the protologue.

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